

Table 1. Summary of studies on circulating microRNAs in breast cancer patients.

miR	Level	Source	Role	cit
miR-1	Upregulation	plasma	Cardiotoxicity - increasing circulating levels during CHT containing DOX and PXL associated with a decrease in LVEF	17
miR-7a	Downregulation	plasma	In comparison to HC (before CHT); increase after treatment	18
	Downregulation	serum	In comparison to HC and pts with benign lesions	19
	Upregulation	serum	In HER2-pos vs. HER2-neg subtype	20
miR-7c	Downregulation	serum	In comparison to HC	21
	Downregulation	serum	In comparison to HC; no diff. between ER-pos and ER-neg BC	22
miR-9	Upregulation	serum	In comparison to HC; in HER2-positive vs. HER2-negative BC	23
miR-10b	Upregulation	plasma	In comparison to HC (before CHT); decrease after Tx	18
miR-16	Downregulation	serum	In comparison to HC	24
miR-17	Downregulation	serum	pCR after neoadjuvant CT	25
miR-18b	Upregulation	serum	Predictive for tumor relapse and OS	26
miR-19a	Upregulation	serum	Resistance to neoadjuvant CT in LUM A	14
miR-19b	Downregulation	serum	pCR after neoadjuvant CT	25
miR-21	Upregulation	plasma	In comparison to HC (before CHT), decrease after Tx	18
	Upregulation	serum	In comparison to HC (before CHT)	21
miR-27a	Upregulation	serum	Higher CS and histological grade, ER-neg, HER2-pos	27
miR-29b	Downregulation	plasma	In comparison to HC	28
miR-30b	Downregulation	serum	pCR after neoadjuvant CT	25
miR-34a	Downregulation	serum	Response to neoadjuvant CT, longer DFS	12
miR-99a	Downregulation	serum	Shorter OS, higher TNM stage	15
miR-106b	Upregulation	plasma	In comparison with benign breast lesions; Shorter DFS & OS	29
miR-122	Upregulation	plasma	In comparison to HC	30
miR-125b	Upregulation	serum	Response to neoadjuvant CT, longer DFS	11
	Upregulation	serum	Higher number of metastatic lymph nodes	20
	Upregulation	serum	In comparison to HC	16,24
	Upregulation	serum	Resistance to neoadjuvant CHT	31
miR-129	Downregulation	serum	Shorter OS	32
miR-141	Upregulation	plasma	Predictive for shorter PFS & OS	33
miR-145	Upregulation	serum	In comparison to HC (before CHT)	16
miR-146a	Downregulation	plasma	In patients with sentinel lymph nodes metastases vs. N0	34
miR-155	Upregulation	plasma	In comparison to HC (before CHT)	18
	Upregulation	plasma	In comparison to HC; higher CS in BC (CS III vs. II; II vs. I)	18
	Downregulation	serum	In comparison to healthy controls	21,24
	Downregulation	serum	Response to Tx	35
	Downregulation	plasma	Response to Tx	18
miR-195	Upregulation	whole blood	In comparison to HC; larger breast tumors; breast cancer-specific	36
	Downregulation	serum	In comparison to HC and benign lesions	19
	Downregulation	serum	In comparison to HC; increase with response to neoadjuvant CT	37
	Downregulation	plasma	Metastatic LUM A BC in comparison to local BC	38
miR-200a	Upregulation	serum	Higher number of metastatic lymph nodes	20
	Upregulation	plasma	Predictive for shorter PFS & OS	33
miR-200b	Upregulation	plasma	Predictive for shorter PFS & OS	33
miR-200c	Upregulation	plasma	In metastatic BC vs. locally advanced BC	39
	Upregulation	plasma	Predictive for shorter PFS & OS	33
miR-205	Upregulation	serum	Resistance to neoadjuvant CT in LUM A	14
miR-210	Downregulation	serum	In comparison to HC (before CHT)	16
miR-222	Upregulation	serum	Shorter DFS & OS; lower rates of pCR; trastuzumab-resistance	40
miR-326	Downregulation	plasma	In patients with sentinel lymph nodes metastases vs. N0	34
miR-373	Upregulation	serum	In comparison to HC (before CHT)	16
miR-451	Downregulation	serum	During neoadjuvant CT in responders	13
miR-455	Downregulation	serum	In comparison with HC, In pts with LN metastases vs N0 Infiltrating carcinoma vs. carcinoma in situ	41

Abbreviations: miR – microRNA; cit – citation; CHT – chemotherapy; DOX – doxorubicin; PXL – paclitaxel; HC – healthy controls; pts – patients; diff – difference; pos – positive; neg – negative; ER – estrogen receptor; BC – breast cancer; HER2 – human epidermal growth factor receptor 2; Tx – treatment; pCR – pathologic complete response; OS – overall survival; LUM – luminal subtype; DFS – disease-free survival; CS – clinical stage; TNM – TNM staging system; PFS – progression-free survival.